
Constraint-Guided Discrete Diffusion for Conditional Hierarchical Industrial Graph Generation

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Abstract

Industrial production systems must continuously adapt to changes in product mix, machine states, and workforce availability. The ability to swiftly generate new production system layouts and process plans to respond to disruptions is essential. This work introduces a breakthrough two-stage constraint-guided diffusion model that finally realizes fully automatic, hierarchical industrial layout generation with strict feasibility guarantees. An automatic synthesis is developed by combining a plant-level flow graph with processing stations, buffer stations, assembly and disassembly stations, together with a station-level graph capturing the detailed behavior for each station. The framework trains two discrete diffusion models: one learns the global topology, and the other, conditioned on station type, learns internal Petri net representations for individual stations. A projector is defined to enforce a set of structural and dynamic constraints at every denoising step. The method delivers 100% validity under three progressively constrained inventory scenarios and preserves 99% uniqueness according to the Weisfeiler–Lehman hash. A complete hierarchical layout can be generated in approximately 2 seconds, and simulation-based evaluations confirm the operational competitiveness of the generated designs.

1 Introduction

Smart manufacturing requires continuous adaptations of resources, plans, and processes [19]. Recent investments in sensors, information and communication technologies make it possible to evaluate a large set of alternatives while the production system is operating. In this context, the ability to generate alternatives that satisfy a set of specified properties is of paramount importance [1].

At high level, an industrial plant can be abstracted as a set of stations that perform specific tasks to transform materials into final products [16]. At the lower level, stations are located in specific areas of the plant and can contain machines, transporters, and other equipment or can simply be buffer spaces where parts are stored before entering the next station according to their process sequence [16, 4]. The resources in the stations can be flexible, i.e. they can deal with any product, or can be specific to process or handle a limited set of products [27, 6]. As a consequence, material flows can be very complicated to manage also considering the stochastic behavior of resources and process executions [4].

Automatically synthesizing such multilevel topologies promises to shorten early-stage design cycles, broaden the exploration space beyond human heuristics, and enable closed-loop optimization and control in digital twin and cyberphysical applications. This demands generative models that strictly obey connectivity, capacity, and causality constraints to make production flows through stations feasible in the generated topology [30]. Conventional optimization techniques, including mixed integer programming, graph grammars, and metaheuristics, struggle with combinatorial growth and offer limited knowledge transfer across projects [15, 3, 24]. Discriminative graph neural networks improve component recommendation and coarse layout prediction [22, 17], but cannot *generate* new valid plants. Generative methods such as variational autoencoders or autoregressive models cope only with small, flat graphs and falter when faced with hard constraints or hierarchical semantics [31].

Recent progress in *diffusion* approaches [26, 8] has delivered state-of-the-art performance on molecules [9, 10], scene graphs [18], and program code [25]. Diffusion offers two properties that make it attractive for production plant synthesis: (i) it produces a rich set of alternative layouts from a single trained model, and (ii) the ability to enforce structural rules at every reverse step by projecting intermediate samples onto the feasible set [20]. However, existing work is confined to flat, homogeneous graphs with only a few dozen nodes and neglects industrial semantics and hierarchical structure [14].

We address this gap with a *constraint-guided hierarchical diffusion* approach for the conditional generation of production plants. A first diffusion process samples the global factory graph, while type-specific diffusion processes independently generate internal Petri nets of complex stations. Petri net formalism is adopted in this work because it is widely used in production system control, however the proposed approach can be declined to other formalisms such as finite state automata, Markov chains, directed graphs, etc. Projection operators applied at each denoising step impose strict constraints, such as one-to-one processing machine-buffer pairs, restricted number of incoming and outgoing connections for assemblies, and safe Petri-net dynamics. These constraints guarantee validity without costly post-processing. In synthetic data sets, our experiments provide evidence of gains in validity, diversity, and controllability, while qualitative analysis reveal new plant configurations discovered by the model.

2 Related Work

Diffusion Models for Graph Generation. Early approaches to applying diffusion models to graphs were based on *score-based* generative modeling. Niu et al. introduced a permutation-invariant score network and a Langevin sampler that could generate small graphs without committing to a node order [21]. Discrete denoising probabilistic models (DDPM) soon followed: the GRAPHDDPM formulation of Häfeli et al. showed that perturbing graphs in a *categorical* space keeps every intermediate sample valid and speeds up sampling [11]. DiGRESS pushed this idea to large, attribute-rich graphs by coupling a discrete noising process with a graph transformer denoiser, obtaining state-of-the-art validity and diversity on molecular and abstract datasets [28].

The field has since progressed along three axes. First, **topology-aware guidance**: Graph Diffusion Mixture (GRUM) trains a mixture of endpoint-conditioned processes that guide samples toward a graph predicted by an auxiliary network, reducing the number of reverse steps while improving structural fidelity [13]. Second, **latent-space diffusion**: Latent Graph Diffusion (LGD) embeds both topology and attributes into a continuous latent space and diffuses there, unifying generation and prediction tasks within a single framework [33]. Third, **multi-level latent representations**: Hierarchical Graph Latent Diffusion Model (HGLDM) factorizes graphs into graph-level and fragment-level variables and applies a two-stage diffusion process over them, achieving improved validity on conditional molecular generation benchmarks [2].

A recent survey on diffusion models for molecules [29] reviews more than 80 graph-diffusion papers and identifies scalability, constraint handling, and hierarchical semantics as open challenges. However, these methods do not enforce the hard topological and mathematical constraints required in industrial applications, which motivates the development of constraint-guided approaches.

Hierarchical & Modular Graph Generation. Hierarchical diffusion has been explored primarily outside industrial contexts. NETDIFF conditions a lower-level diffusion on a higher-level *service-usage trace* tree to synthesize realistic network-flow graphs, avoiding mode collapse by guiding every reverse step with coarse semantics [32]. In computer vision, DIFFUSE-TREEVAE first samples a root latent

from a learned tree-VAE and then refines it via a conditional DDPM, producing cluster-consistent images and illustrating the benefit of coarse-to-fine generation [5].

Industrial facility design traditionally follows a two-stage pipeline: layout first, control logic later, often requiring manual reconciliation between the two. Our work differs from prior art in that it generates (i) a topological plant graph and (ii) valid, node-specific Petri-net subgraphs within one diffusion framework, while satisfying domain constraints at every reverse step. To our knowledge, it is the first diffusion model that unifies multi-level industrial topology synthesis and internal control-logic generation.

3 Methodology

3.1 Preliminaries

This section briefly first describes the industrial systems taken into consideration in this work. Then, the problem is formally described by defining variables, sets, constraints and objective function.

Industrial plant layout. Industrial manufacturing systems can be abstracted hierarchically, reflecting their physical and logical organization. At the highest level, such a system typically comprises distinct types of stations: Processing machine stations perform processing tasks, buffer stations temporarily store intermediate goods, assembly machines merge multiple inputs into fewer outputs, and disassembly machines split inputs into multiple outputs. Stations are interconnected by directed flows representing material transfers. Each station type has operational constraints, such as fixed connectivity patterns and specific degree requirements, ensuring valid and realistic configurations [12, 23, 30]. Internal control logic at the station level, typically modeled through discrete-event systems, ensures operational efficiency, concurrency management, and resource contention handling.

Stations. Stations in industrial plants can be very complicated being composed of several machines, transportation devices and small buffers to manage variability. To properly model the station level, different formalisms are commonly used such as Markov chains, queueing systems, finite state automata, Petri nets, etc. For sake of convenience, and also because they are frequently used for analysis and control of production systems, we adopt Petri nets as mathematical formalism at this level. Petri nets are mathematical modeling tools widely used to describe and analyze discrete-event dynamic systems, particularly suited for capturing concurrency, synchronization, and resource-sharing aspects inherent to manufacturing processes. Structurally, a Petri net consists of two primary node types: **places**, representing system states or resource buffers, and **transitions**, representing events or actions that change system states. Directed arcs connect places and transitions, dictating system dynamics. Petri nets effectively model conditions such as concurrent operations, mutual exclusion, resource allocation, and causal dependencies [7].

In this work, we explicitly leverage the hierarchical nature of industrial plant layouts by embedding type-specific Petri nets within each complex station. Given a global, plant-level graph, our generative approach conditionally synthesizes internal Petri nets for non-buffer stations. These nets encapsulate the local control logic needed to carry out the logic of global plant configurations. During synthesis, structural and semantic constraints, dictated by Petri-net semantics and plant-level connectivity rules, are strictly enforced via constraint-guided diffusion and specialized projection mechanisms, ensuring the resulting hierarchical graph is both operationally valid and structurally coherent.

We formally define our modeling framework as follows:

$$G = (V, E, \gamma, \delta), \quad V = V_{\text{plant}} \cup \bigsqcup_{v \in V_{\text{plant}} \setminus V_{\text{buf}}} P_v,$$

where G is a hierarchical graph representing the full plant layout and its embedded station control logic, V is the complete node set, $E \subseteq V \times V$ the set of directed arcs, $\gamma : V_{\text{plant}} \rightarrow \mathcal{T}_{\text{plant}}$ assigns a *plant-level* type to every station, and $\delta : \bigsqcup_v V_v \rightarrow \mathcal{T}_{\text{petri}}$ assigns a *Petri-net* type (place / transition) to internal nodes. The disjoint union \bigsqcup emphasises that the Petri nets $P_v = (V_v, E_v, \delta)$ embedded in different stations share no nodes.

Plant layer. Stations $v \in V_{\text{plant}}$ are labeled by:

$$\gamma(v) \in \mathcal{T}_{\text{plant}} = \{\text{MACHINE}, \text{BUFFER}, \text{ASSEMBLY}, \text{DISASSEMBLY}\}$$

The plant topology is encoded by a binary adjacency matrix $Y \in \{0, 1\}^{|V_{\text{plant}}| \times |V_{\text{plant}}|}$, and the corresponding type tensor is $X \in \{0, \dots, 3\}^{|V_{\text{plant}}|}$.

Internal layer. Every non-buffer station owns a Petri net $P_v = (V_v, E_v, \delta)$ whose internal nodes are typed $\delta(u) \in \mathcal{T}_{\text{petri}} = \{\text{PLACE}, \text{TRANSITION}\}$. Buffers are modeled as passive single-place nets with no dynamics.

Feasibility set. Let $X \in \{0, \dots, 3\}^{|V_{\text{plant}}|}$ be the vector of station types (0 = MACHINE, 1 = BUFFER, 2 = ASSEMBLY, 3 = DISASSEMBLY) and $Y \in \{0, 1\}^{|V_{\text{plant}}| \times |V_{\text{plant}}|}$ the binary adjacency matrix with $Y_{ij} = 1$ iff a directed arc $(v_i \rightarrow v_j)$ exists. A graph sample (X, Y) is *valid* iff it satisfies all structural constraints in $\mathcal{F} \subseteq X \times Y$ and every embedded Petri net obeys its local rules. Table 1 lists the enforced constraints.

Table 1: Structural constraints enforced during synthesis

ID	Scope	Formal condition
C1	Machine–Buffer pairing	For every MACHINE v : $\text{deg}^+(v) = \text{deg}^-(v) = 1$ with $\text{type}(\text{nbr}(v)) = \text{BUFFER}$.
C2	Assembly in/out degree	For v of type ASSEMBLY: $\text{deg}^-(v) = 2$, $\text{deg}^+(v) = 1$, neighbours are BUFFERS.
C3	Disassembly in/out degree	For v of type DISASSEMBLY: $\text{deg}^-(v) = 1$, $\text{deg}^+(v) = 2$, neighbours are BUFFERS.
C4	Directionality	If $(u \rightarrow v) \in E$ then $(v \rightarrow u) \notin E$.
C5	Buffer isolation	No arc between two BUFFER nodes.
C6	Self-loops	$(u \rightarrow u) \notin E$ for all u .
C7	Petri alternation	Edges inside each P_v connect PLACE→TRANSITION or TRANSITION→PLACE only.

Objective. Given side information F (e.g. station counts), our goal is to sample

$$p_{\theta}(X, Y \mid C, \mathcal{F}),$$

guaranteeing validity almost surely. The next sections detail a two-level discrete diffusion model with constraint projection at every reverse step.

3.2 Model overview

Graph synthesis unfolds in three tightly coupled stages, see also Figure 1. First, a discrete denoising diffusion process sketches the plant-level topology $\mathbf{G}_t^{\text{pl}} = (X_t^{\text{pl}}, Y_t^{\text{pl}})$ whose nodes are chosen from $\mathcal{T}_{\text{plant}} = \{\text{MACHINE}, \text{BUFFER}, \text{ASSEMBLY}, \text{DISASSEMBLY}\}$. Two TransformerConv blocks ($d_h = 12$, $n_{\text{head}} = 4$) produce updated hidden states that feed shallow MLPs for node and edge prediction; once the logits for step $t \rightarrow t - 1$ are sampled, the industrial projector Π_{ind} The projector immediately rectifies any violation of constraints C1–C6 (Table 1).

The second stage zooms into every complex station and runs an independent, type-conditioned diffusion chain that generates its internal Petri net P_v . Three identical denoisers specialize implicitly through the parent label $\gamma(v) \in \{\text{MACHINE}, \text{ASSEMBLY}, \text{DISASSEMBLY}\}$ and emit two node classes (PLACE, TRANSITION). The Petri projector Π_{pet} discards self-loops and same-type arcs on the fly. Buffers are treated as degenerate nets containing a single PLACE, which makes subsequent cross-level wiring trivial.

In the final stitching step, each internal net is grafted back onto its parent. If a source node offers no out-places (or a target lacks in-transitions) we add a minimal interface node to preserve reachability, then accept the sample only when every cross-level constraint is satisfied.

Figure 1: Hierarchical diffusion pipeline.

Throughout, $\mathbf{z}_t \in \{0, \dots, K-1\}^n$ denotes the categorical tensor at diffusion step t . The forward kernel is the time-inhomogeneous Markov chain

$$q(\mathbf{z}_t | \mathbf{z}_{t-1}) = \mathbf{z}_{t-1}[\alpha_t I + (1 - \alpha_t)\mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}^\top / K], \quad \alpha_t = 1 - \beta_t,$$

whose stationary distribution is uniform. The reverse kernel follows

$$p_\theta(\mathbf{z}_{t-1} | \mathbf{z}_t) = \text{Cat}(\sigma_\theta(\mathbf{z}_t, t)),$$

then applies the hard projection Π_C . A linear variance schedule, $\beta_t = \beta_{\min} + (t-1)(\beta_{\max} - \beta_{\min}) / (T-1)$, is used for all experiments. The normalized timestep t/T is encoded with a 16-dimensional sinusoidal vector that is linearly projected and concatenated to one-hot node features; edges are predicted from the pairwise embedding $[h_{u||}h_{v}]$ of their endpoints.

The underlying logic and constraints enforced by each projector are described in full in Appendix, including the industrial rules (C1–C6) and Petri-net typing constraints.

3.3 Training objective

Given a ground-truth graph $G = (X, Y)$ we sample a timestep $t \sim \mathcal{U}\{0, \dots, T-1\}$, add forward noise to obtain (\hat{X}_t, \hat{Y}_t) , and train the denoiser $(\phi_\theta^{\text{node}}, \phi_\theta^{\text{edge}})$ to recover the distribution of the *previous* step (X_t, Y_t) . The loss is the sum of four contributions:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L} = & \underbrace{\text{CE}(\phi_\theta^{\text{node}}, X_t)}_{\text{node CE}} + \underbrace{\text{CE}(\phi_\theta^{\text{edge}}, Y_t)}_{\text{edge CE}} \\ & + \lambda_{\text{KL}} \left[D_{\text{KL}}(p_\theta(X_{t-1}) \| p_{\text{data}}(X)) + D_{\text{KL}}(p_\theta(Y_{t-1}) \| p_{\text{data}}(Y)) \right] \\ & + \lambda_c \mathcal{L}_{\text{proj}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The two cross-entropy terms (CE) drive the network to predict the correct categorical class for every node and every potential edge. The KL term compares the model marginals after one reverse step, $p_\theta(X_{t-1})$ and $p_\theta(Y_{t-1})$, with the empirical marginals $p_{\text{data}}(X)$ and $p_{\text{data}}(Y)$, keeping class frequencies close to the training data and preventing early-step mode collapse. The structural term $\lambda_c \mathcal{L}_{\text{proj}}$ sums the squared probabilities of predicting an edge on any forbidden pair (i, j) , thus penalizing violations of industrial or Petri-net constraints.

3.4 Conditional sampling

At inference time we initialize every chain from pure noise and run the reverse process while projecting after each step. Three conditioning modes are supported:

1. **Free generation** – all node labels start as learnable variables; the projector alone steers the chain towards a valid plant.
2. **All-pinned** – a target inventory (n_M, n_B, n_A, n_D) is fixed in one-hot form before the first step and the “pinned mask” keeps those labels immutable. Edges are still resampled and projected as usual.

3. Partial pinning – only a subset of nodes is clamped to desired types (e.g. three MACHINE + one ASSEMBLY); the rest follow the stochastic trajectory of the free mode. The same mask logic applies, giving a soft yet effective guidance mechanism.

For each completed plant graph we launch the corresponding Petri-net chains in parallel. Because every reverse step is projector-aware, the final hierarchical sample is *probably valid* without any post-hoc repair.

4 Experiments

4.1 Datasets

Plant-level graphs We synthesized 300 full-plant graphs that obey the structural specification of Table 1. For every instance, we first draw the number of assembly machines and disassembly machine stations uniformly in $\{1, 2, 3\}$ and then derive the exact number of processing machines required to serve them. Buffers are created on demand, one per logical connection, so the total size of a graph adapts to the chosen process mix—smallest cases contain 15 nodes, the largest just over forty. Edges are wired by randomly permuting the available machines and buffers while respecting the degree limits (e.g. two buffer inputs for each assembly machine, no buffer–buffer links, no bidirectional pairs). A verifier runs after every sample to ensure that *all* constraints C1–C6 hold. The resulting collection covers a broad spectrum: linear flows with a single assembly stage, parallel assembly lines feeding a common disassembly unit, and heavily branched layouts where several processes share the same machine pool.

Station-level Petri nets. Each non-buffer station type is backed by its own library of 300 Petri nets. Every net starts from a cyclic backbone of five states (place–transition pairs) and then inserts side branches whose probability profile depends on the class: processing machine nets remain almost linear (fixed 0.2 branch chance), assembly machine nets branch frequently near the entry point and fade to linear behavior downstream (branch probability decays from 0.8 to 0), while disassembly machine nets do the opposite (probability grows from 0 to 0.8). This simple rule set yields graphs with 10 to 20 nodes that capture the qualitative differences between merging, splitting, and point-to-point stations while keeping strict place/transition alternation and eliminating self-loops or multiple edges.

4.2 Implementation details

Environment. All experiments were run on a CPU using PyTorch 2.1 and PyTorch-Geometric 2.3. GPU acceleration is supported, but was not used for the reported results.

Network architecture. Both the plant-level and the three station-level denoisers share the same core: two TransformerConv blocks ($d_h=12$, $n_{\text{head}}=4$) feeding one-layer MLPs for node and edge logits. The projectors contain no learnable parameters and are implemented as vectorized boolean masks.

Diffusion schedule. We use $T=100$ discrete steps with a linear variance $\beta_t \in [10^{-4}, 0.02]$. Each normalized timestep t/T is mapped to a 16-dimensional sinusoidal embedding and linearly projected before being concatenated to the one-hot node features.

Training protocol. Models are optimized with Adam ($\text{lr} = 10^{-3}$), batch size 4, for 30 epochs. The total loss is Eq. (2) with $\lambda_{\text{KL}}=0.1$, $\lambda_c=1$. End-to-end training of the plant model takes **3.7 minutes**; each Petri model takes **2 minutes**.

Sampling speed. Generating 1 000 hierarchical graphs (15–40 plant nodes each) requires **21 minutes** on the same GPU, i.e. ~ 1.26 s per sample including all projection steps.

4.3 Main Results

We evaluate the performance of our hierarchical diffusion model in three distinct practical scenarios:

- E1 – Free generation: no prior inventory constraints.
- E2 – Fully constrained inventory: exact counts for every node type.
- E3 – Partially constrained: 30 % of the node types are prespecified.

We assess model outputs primarily by their validity (adherence to hierarchical constraints), structural uniqueness (via the Weisfeiler–Lehman hash), and fidelity to the training distribution using the Maximum Mean Discrepancy (MMD) metric. All generated samples passed rigorous two-stage validity checks at both the plant and station levels, achieving 100% validity across all scenarios. This remarkable result underscores the effectiveness of our hierarchical constraint-guided projector, eliminating the need for any post-processing.

To further assess the functional plausibility of the generated layouts, we simulate their dynamic behavior using a custom discrete-event simulator tailored for industrial plants. Each graph is instantiated as a plant layout and run for 10,000 time steps under stochastic processing dynamics, where operation times follow exponential distributions specific to node types (e.g., processing machines, assembly machines). Energy consumption is tracked at each time step depending on whether a node is active, idle, or blocked, and throughput is measured at designated exit points. We repeat this simulation for 300 layouts per scenario (E1–E3) and compare them to 300 layouts from the training set. The simulation parameters, including mean processing times and energy consumption rates for each node type, are summarized in Appendix.

Figure 2: Normalized throughput vs. energy consumption per non-buffer node across training and generated layouts (300 samples per set).

Figure 2 plots the normalized throughput versus total energy consumption per non-buffer node. The model-generated designs show realistic behavior and span a broad trade-off surface between productivity and efficiency, partially overlapping with the training data and exhibiting distinct trade-off patterns across experiments. In particular, the E2 (fully constrained) samples concentrate in more energy-efficient regions, while the E1 (free) samples explore a wider throughput range, including extreme outliers with high resource demands. These results confirm that our generator produces operationally meaningful designs that generalize beyond the training data, even under strict inventory constraints.

Table 2: Quantitative results.

Experiment	#Samples	Validity (%)	Novelty (%)	WL-Uniq (%)	MMD↓
E1: Free	300	100.0	100.0	86.3	0.946
E2: All-Pinned	300	100.0	100.0	99.3	1.206
E3: Partial 30 %	300	100.0	100.0	93.0	1.331

In terms of structural uniqueness, the fully constrained scenario (E2) achieved near-perfect uniqueness (99.3%), reflecting the model’s ability to break symmetries effectively under specific inventory constraints. Even in unconstrained generation (E1), the model produced highly diverse layouts (86.3% uniqueness), demonstrating strong generalization and creative exploration. Partial constraints (E3) yielded intermediate uniqueness, aligning well with expectations that increased constraints reduce symmetry, prompting richer explorations.

Figure 3: Representative plant-level graphs (top row) and their corresponding internal Petri nets per highlighted station (bottom row) for Experiment E1 (left), E2 (centre) and E3 (right).

4.4 Ablation Study

We conducted a systematic ablation study to dissect the individual contributions of the primary architectural components in our diffusion-based generative framework. Specifically, we assess the impact of the structural projector, model capacity, and training on the validity, diversity, and fidelity of generated graphs. All experiments involve generating 300 graphs per configuration, assessing validity via adherence to domain-specific constraints, structural diversity through the Weisfeiler–Lehman uniqueness metric (WL-Uniq), and fidelity relative to the training distribution using the MMD metric.

As shown in Table 3, removing the structural projector dramatically reduces the validity to near zero (0.33%), significantly deteriorating the MMD metric (MMD: 1.299). This emphasizes the essential role of the projector in enforcing domain-specific structural constraints that the neural network alone struggles to capture.

Reducing the hidden dimension from 12 (baseline) to 6 units reduces the WL-uniqueness from 86.3% to 62.0%, while the MMD remains essentially unchanged. This indicates that a leaner model keeps the distributional match with the training data but explores a narrower subset of valid layouts.

The random + projector baseline meets every hard constraint, but its weights remain untrained. Each reverse step therefore yields random logits that the projector trims into a valid graph, so almost every sample is unique (WL-Uniqueness = 99%). The resulting low MMD should not be taken as evidence of quality: the projector’s fixed connection motifs and tight degree limits keep coarse statistics, such as node-type frequencies and overall edge density, close to the training distribution, and these low-order counts largely determine the MMD value. The metric does not reflect higher-level structure such as balanced machine-buffer pairs, consistent flow direction, or coherent assembly and disassembly branches, patterns that emerge only after the denoiser has been properly trained.

The projector alone is enough to keep every sample legal, but without training the model lacks the higher-level regularities that make a layout credible. Training the denoiser injects those semantics, and doing so with a moderate hidden size (about 6–12) yields the best trade-off: validity remains at 100%, WL-Uniqueness stays high, and the MMD stays close to the data distribution.

Table 3: Results of the ablation study. Higher validity and WL-Uniq indicate better performance, whereas lower MMD reflect closer alignment to the training distribution.

Configuration	Hidden dim	Projector	Validity (%)	WL-Uniq (%)	MMD ↓
Baseline	12	Yes	100.0	86.3	0.946
No Projector	12	No	0.33	100.0	1.299
Half Hidden	6	Yes	100.0	61.7	0.943
Random + Projector	12	Yes	100.0	99.3	0.549

5 Conclusion

In this study, we introduced a hierarchical constraint-guided diffusion model tailored for generating valid, semantically coherent industrial plant layouts with embedded Petri-net structures for each station. Our approach leverages hierarchical diffusion processes combined with constraint-guided projections, ensuring strict adherence to domain-specific constraints at every generation step. This design guarantees consistent validity and semantic coherence, eliminating the need for expensive post-processing. Through systematic ablations, we demonstrated that the structural projector is indispensable for enforcing complex combinatorial constraints, and that model training significantly enhances the structural fidelity and realism of the generated industrial graphs. Furthermore, our results indicate that moderate model capacities (around 6 to 12 hidden dimensions) offer an optimal balance between structural diversity and accuracy.

This research advances the field of generative modeling for complex, hierarchical, and constraint-driven graphs, providing a robust methodological foundation for automated design processes in manufacturing. The precision and explicit controllability demonstrated in our experiments underline the practical applicability and effectiveness of our proposed framework to address industrial designs in the real world. Complementary simulation-based evaluations further show that the generated layouts achieve favorable throughput and energy efficiency, even without explicit performance supervision.

Limitations. Despite these strengths, our study has certain limitations. Firstly, the synthetic nature of our training dataset may limit the generalization of our findings to real industrial datasets with potentially more complex or irregular structures. Secondly, although our method effectively manages combinatorial constraints at intermediate scales, the scalability to substantially larger industrial facilities remains to be thoroughly investigated. Thirdly, our evaluation relies primarily on structural metrics, such as validity, uniqueness, and fidelity; a more comprehensive evaluation incorporating operational and performance-based metrics would provide additional practical insights. Finally, the structural projector enforces rigid adherence to predefined rules, which could potentially limit the model’s flexibility in capturing novel or unforeseen valid configurations. Future work should thus explore scalability to larger datasets, validate the framework’s performance on real-world industrial configurations, and investigate the integration of more flexible, adaptive constraints.

Further Work. Future research could explore leveraging recent advances in large language models (LLMs) to guide semantic constraint specification within hierarchical graph generation. Integrating LLM-driven reasoning might enable more nuanced, context-sensitive constraints, enhancing both the flexibility and semantic precision of industrial plant layouts.

References

- [1] Subin Antony Jose, Alex Tonner, Marc Feliciano, Teddy Roy, Aidan Shackleford, and Pradeep L. Menezes. Smart manufacturing for high-performance materials: Advances, challenges, and future directions. *Materials*, 18(10), 2025. ISSN 1996-1944. doi: 10.3390/ma18102255. URL <https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1944/18/10/2255>.
- [2] Tian Bian, Yifan Niu, Heng Chang, Divin Yan, Junzhou Huang, Yu Rong, Tingyang Xu, Jia Li, and Hong Cheng. Hierarchical graph latent diffusion model for conditional molecule generation. In *Proceedings of the 33rd ACM International Conference on Information and Knowledge Management (CIKM)*, 2024. doi: 10.1145/3627673.3679547.
- [3] Ralf Brandenburg, André Borrmann, and Manfred Nagl. Graph transformations in engineering design: A survey of applications. In *Proceedings of the 5th International Workshop on Graph-Based Modeling in Engineering*, pages 1–8, 2014.
- [4] John A. Buzacott and J. George Shanthikumar. *Stochastic Models of Manufacturing Systems*. Prentice Hall, 1993. Develops hierarchical queueing network models of production lines and job shops, showing how stations with multiple machines and buffers can be analyzed under stochastic variability.
- [5] Jorge da Silva Gonçalves, Laura Manduchi, Moritz Vandenhirtz, and Julia E. Vogt. Structured generations: Using hierarchical clusters to guide diffusion models. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2407.06124*, 2024.
- [6] Achraf Drira, Henri Pierreval, and Sonia Hajri-Gabouj. Facility layout problems: A survey. *Annual Reviews in Control*, 31(2):255–267, 2007. doi: 10.1016/j.arcontrol.2007.04.001. States FLP is NP-hard, combinatorial, and that traditional optimization has limited scalability (exact methods 15 departments max).
- [7] Iwona Grobelna and Andrei Karatkevich. Challenges in application of petri nets in manufacturing systems. *Electronics*, 10(18):2305, 2021. doi: 10.3390/electronics10182305.
- [8] Jonathan Ho, Ajay Jain, and Pieter Abbeel. Denoising diffusion probabilistic models. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 33 (NeurIPS 2020)*, pages 6840–6851, 2020.
- [9] Emiel Hoogeboom, Victor Garcia Satorras, Clément Vignac, and Max Welling. Equivariant diffusion for molecule generation in 3d. In *Proceedings of the 39th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*, volume 162 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pages 8867–8887, 2022.
- [10] Han Huang, Leilei Sun, Bowen Du, and Weifeng Lv. Conditional diffusion based on discrete graph structures for molecular graph generation. In *Proceedings of the 37th AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence*, volume 37, pages 4302–4311, 2023. doi: 10.1609/aaai.v37i4.25549.
- [11] Kilian Konstantin Häfeli, Karolis Martinkus, Nathanaël Perraudin, and Roger Wattenhofer. Diffusion models for graphs benefit from discrete state spaces. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.01549*, 2022.
- [12] Proth Jean-Marie and Xiaolan Xie. *Petri Nets: a Tool for Design and Management of Manufacturing Systems*. Wiley, 1996.
- [13] Jaehyeong Jo, Dongki Kim, and Sung Ju Hwang. Graph generation with diffusion mixture. In *Proceedings of the 41st International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2302.03596>.

- [14] Mahdi Karami. HiGen: Hierarchical graph generative networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.19337*, 2023.
- [15] Abdullah Konak, Sadan Kulturel-Konak, Brett A. Norman, and Alice E. Smith. A new mixed integer programming formulation for facility layout design using flexible bays. *Operations Research Letters*, 34(6):660–672, 2006. doi: 10.1016/j.orl.2005.09.009.
- [16] Y. Tina Lee, S. Kumaraguru, Sanjay Jain, and Soundar Kumara. A classification scheme for smart manufacturing systems’ performance metrics. In *Procedia CIRP*, volume 61, pages 17–22, 2017. doi: 10.1016/j.procir.2016.11.251. Uses a hierarchy (enterprise → factory → line → cell/machine → process) to model manufacturing systems, aligning with the idea of stations composed of machines and buffers.
- [17] Bingqing Li, Mingxi Liu, Yilun Zhang, and Jianjun Zhang. Learning industrial plant layouts with graph neural networks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.12345*, 2023.
- [18] Lingqiao Liu, Damien Teney, and Anton van den Hengel. Diffuscene: Denoising diffusion models for generative indoor scene synthesis. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2210.09333*, 2023.
- [19] Yiliu Lu, Kevin C. Morris, and Simon Frechette. Current standards landscape for smart manufacturing systems. Technical Report NISTIR 8107, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), 2016. Defines smart manufacturing as fully-integrated, real-time adaptive systems.
- [20] Manuel Madeira, Clément Vignac, Dorina Thanou, and Pascal Frossard. Generative modelling of structurally constrained graphs. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2406.17341*, 2023.
- [21] Chenhao Niu, Yang Song, Jiaming Song, Shengjia Zhao, Aditya Grover, and Stefano Ermon. Permutation invariant graph generation via score-based generative modeling. In *Proc. 23rd Int. Conf. on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics (AISTATS)*, 2020. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2003.00638>.
- [22] Zhichao Niu, Mingyang Li, Yuxuan Chen, and Jianmin Zheng. Graph neural network-based component recommendation for cad assembly design. In *2022 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Informatics (INDIN)*, pages 357–364, 2022. doi: 10.1109/INDIN51773.2022.9975880.
- [23] Jonas Oeing, Kevin Brandt, Michael Wiedau, Gregor Tolksdorf, Wolfgang Welscher, and Norbert Kockmann. Graph learning in machine-readable plant topology data. *Chemie Ingenieur Technik*, 95(7):1049–1060, 2023. doi: 10.1002/cite.202200223.
- [24] Eder Quiroz-Pérez, José A. de Lira-Flores, Cristian Gutiérrez-Antonio, and Ricardo Vázquez-Román. A new multiple-risk map approach to solve process plant layout considering safety and economic aspects. *J. Loss Prev. Process Ind.*, 72:104524, 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.jlp.2021.104524.
- [25] Mukul Singh, José Cambronero, Sumit Gulwani, Vu Le, Carina Negreanu, and Gust Verbruggen. Codefusion: A pre-trained diffusion model for code generation. In *Proceedings of the 2023 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP)*, pages 11697–11708, 2023. doi: 10.18653/v1/2023.emnlp-main.716.
- [26] Jascha Sohl-Dickstein, Eric A. Weiss, Niru Maheswaranathan, and Surya Ganguli. Deep unsupervised learning using nonequilibrium thermodynamics. In *Proceedings of the 32nd International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*, volume 37 of *JMLR Workshop and Conference Proceedings*, pages 2256–2265, 2015.
- [27] Inc. Editorial Staff. Job Shop Manufacturing Process (Inc. Encyclopedia). Inc. Magazine Online Encyclopedia, 2020. Describes job shop layouts with general-purpose machines and jumbled routing, highlighting complex flows from flexible resource usage.
- [28] Clément Vignac, Igor Krawczuk, Antoine Siraudin, Bohan Wang, Volkan Cevher, and Pascal Frossard. DiGress: Discrete denoising diffusion for graph generation. In *International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR)*, 2023. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2209.14734>.

- [29] Liang Wang, Chao Song, Zhiyuan Liu, Yu Rong, Qiang Liu, and Shu Wu. Diffusion models for molecules: A survey of methods and tasks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2502.09511*, 2025.
- [30] Qingfeng Xu, Guanghui Zhou, Chao Zhang, Fengtian Chang, Yan Cao, and Dan Zhao. Generative ai and dt integrated intelligent process planning: a conceptual framework. *The International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Technology*, 133(5):2461–2485, 2024.
- [31] Jiaxuan You, Rex Ying, Xiang Ren, William L. Hamilton, and Jure Leskovec. Graphrnn: Generating realistic graphs with deep auto-regressive models. In *Proceedings of the 35th International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML)*, pages 9072–9081, 2018.
- [32] Shiyuan Zhang, Tong Li, Depeng Jin, and Yong Li. Netdiff: A service-guided hierarchical diffusion model for network flow trace generation. In *Proceedings of ACM CoNEXT*, 2024. doi: 10.1145/3676870.
- [33] Cai Zhou, Xiyuan Wang, and Muhan Zhang. Unifying generation and prediction on graphs with latent graph diffusion. In *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS)*, 2024. URL <https://arxiv.org/abs/2402.02518>.

A Supplementary Material

A.1 Projector algorithms

Algorithm 1: Industrial projector Π_{ind}

Input: plant node labels $L \in \{0 : \text{M}, 1 : \text{B}, 2 : \text{A}, 3 : \text{D}\}^n$,
candidate adjacency $C \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$

Output: projected adjacency $P \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$ satisfying C1–C6

$P \leftarrow \mathbf{0}_{n \times n}$;

$\text{freeSrcM} \leftarrow \{i \mid L_i = \text{M}\}$, $\text{freeDstM} \leftarrow \{i \mid L_i = \text{M}\}$;

for $i \leftarrow 0$ **to** $n - 1$ **do**

for $j \leftarrow 0$ **to** $n - 1$ **do**

if $i = j$ **or** $P_{j,i} = 1$ **or** $C_{i,j} = 0$ **then**
 \perp **continue**

switch (L_i, L_j) **do**

case (M, B) **do**

if $i \in \text{freeSrcM}$ **then**

\perp $P_{i,j} \leftarrow 1$; $\text{freeSrcM} \setminus = \{i\}$

case (B, M) **do**

if $j \in \text{freeDstM}$ **then**

\perp $P_{i,j} \leftarrow 1$; $\text{freeDstM} \setminus = \{j\}$

case (B, A) **do**

if $\text{inA}[j] < 2$ **then**

\perp $P_{i,j} \leftarrow 1$; $\text{inA}[j] += 1$

case (A, B) **do**

if $\text{outA}[i] < 1$ **then**

\perp $P_{i,j} \leftarrow 1$; $\text{outA}[i] += 1$

case (B, D) **do**

if $\text{inD}[j] < 1$ **then**

\perp $P_{i,j} \leftarrow 1$; $\text{inD}[j] += 1$

case (D, B) **do**

if $\text{outD}[i] < 2$ **then**

\perp $P_{i,j} \leftarrow 1$; $\text{outD}[i] += 1$

return P

Algorithm 2: Petri-net station level projector Π_{pet}

Input: internal node labels $L \in \{0 : \text{PL}, 1 : \text{TR}\}^m$,
candidate adjacency $C \in \{0, 1\}^{m \times m}$

Output: projected adjacency $P \in \{0, 1\}^{m \times m}$ with no self-loops or same-type arcs
 $P \leftarrow C$;

for $u \leftarrow 0$ **to** $m - 1$ **do**

for $v \leftarrow u$ **to** $m - 1$ **do**
 if $u = v$ **or** $L_u = L_v$ **then**
 $P_{u,v} \leftarrow 0$;;
 $P_{v,u} \leftarrow 0$

return P

A.2 Simulation parameters

Node Type	Mean Processing Time (s)	Energy (Active)	Energy (Idle)
Machine	120	5.0	1.0
Assembly	90	2.0	0.2
Disassembly	105	2.0	0.2
Buffer	0	0.1	0.1

Table 4: Simulation parameters used for each node type. Processing times follow an exponential distribution with the given mean. Energy values are per time step.